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PERCEPTIONS OF COUNTERINTELLIGENCE IN CORPORATE AND ACADEMIC SECTORS RISKS, AWARENESS, AND STRATEGIC IMPLICATIONS

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Introduction

The United States is in the middle of an intelligence war. Foreign adversaries, including their intelligence services and state-sponsored actors, employ increasingly sophisticated technologies and methods to access our most valuable innovations and secrets. The importance of implementing counterintelligence (CI) practices across all sectors of American society has never been greater.

As our adversaries increasingly target non-governmental data environments, it has become essential to address security gaps in our nation's critical industries, supply chains, and academic institutions. While the last two decades have seen the widespread adoption of cybersecurity protocols, malign actors continue to evolve their tactics to exploit both technical and human vulnerabilities. Counterintelligence can and should be a vital tool for corporations and academia which have become increasingly vulnerable targets for foreign espionage, theft, sabotage, and influence operations. By providing strategic insights and actionable practices, counterintelligence enables organizations to effectively and efficiently recognize and respond to threats that fall outside the scope of traditional cybersecurity.

This study aims to explore how counterintelligence is perceived in civilian sectors – specifically corporate and academic institutions – in response to escalating intelligence threats. By surveying a diverse range of professionals in the academic and corporate sectors, this study assesses the awareness, attitudes, and institutional barriers to adopting CI practices and seeks to highlight key knowledge gaps and identify opportunities for targeted awareness, training, and investment. The results will inform policy and provide strategic recommendations for building a CI-conscious culture across sectors.

Contextual Overview

Counterintelligence is a critical yet underdeveloped element of the U.S. intelligence apparatus. Despite its importance, CI has only recently started to receive appropriate attention and support, especially from industries vulnerable to foreign exploitation.¹ Misunderstandings about the nature of CI, coupled with vague definitions and unclear methods, have led to distrust and weak collaboration between federal agencies, local law enforcement, and civilian sectors.

There is no formal framework that effectively integrates CI with civilian organizations and institutions. This absence has created a communication and cooperation gap between government agencies, academia, and private industries. While insider threats remain an issue, rapid technological advancements have introduced new opportunities for exploitation.² The CI community is often reactive, struggling to meet policymakers' demands for broader and more proactive responses, which extend beyond traditional CI functions.

Historically, CI has focused on defensive measures that protect known targets.³ While this approach offers some security, it does not anticipate or neutralize threats before they materialize. A shift toward an offensive CI posture, particularly in industries that support U.S. innovation, would better disrupt foreign intelligence efforts.⁴

To address current and emerging threats, CI must extend beyond the intelligence community and be applied broadly across industries that drive innovation. Foreign intelligence

¹ Ellyse Elmer, "Counterintelligence: The Neglected Element," PHC, September 28, 2015, <https://www.phc.edu/intelligencer/the-neglected-element>; Hank Prunckun, "A Grounded Theory of Counterintelligence," *American Intelligence Journal* 29, no. 2 (2011): 7. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26201945>.

² Michael Coyne, "Facing Threats in the 'Fourth Era' of American Counterintelligence," *The Cipher Brief*, April 22, 2025, https://www.thecipherbrief.com/column_article/facing-threats-in-the-fourth-era-of-american-counterintelligence.

³ Ellyse Elmer, "Counterintelligence: The Neglected Element,"

⁴ James M. Olson, "The Ten Commandments of Counterintelligence," CIA, 2001, <https://www.cia.gov/resources/csi/studies-in-intelligence/archives/vol-45-no-5/the-ten-commandments-of-counterintelligence/>.

entities increasingly target soft sectors, including universities and private corporations. Their goal is to steal intellectual property, research, and economic strategies to undermine U.S. competitiveness and weaken national security.

Although awareness of the importance of CI in academic and corporate environments is increasing, significant disconnects remain between these sectors and federal intelligence bodies. This lack of integration leaves these industries vulnerable to cyber and espionage threats. Academic institutions and private companies are particularly difficult to protect. Their open and collaborative nature makes them attractive to foreign actors seeking to exploit innovative research and poses significant challenges in implementing measures that may inhibit information sharing. Malign partnerships and covert operations, including those involving foreign students and researchers, allow adversaries to bypass costly research and development efforts and gain strategic advantages.⁵

Implementing CI programs in these environments presents several challenges. Academics often fear that security measures will impede intellectual freedom and limit international collaboration. Corporations may resist CI initiatives that appear to constrain growth or shareholder interests. Additionally, both sectors frequently lack the financial resources as well as the expertise necessary to apply counterintelligence measures effectively.⁶

⁵ “Additional Questions for George Wesley Street upon His Nomination to Be Director of the National Counterintelligence and Security Center,” United States Senate, accessed July 8, 2025, <https://www.intelligence.senate.gov/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/aphq-gstreet.pdf>.

⁶ Kevin R. Gamache, “Protecting American Innovation: Industry, Academia, and the National Counterintelligence and Security Center” (U.S. Senate Select Committee on Intelligence, September 21, 2022), <https://www.intelligence.senate.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/sites-default-files-documents-qfr-kgamache-092122.pdf>; Federal Bureau of Investigation, “The FBI’s College and University Security Effort” (FBI Academic Alliance Program), accessed October 2, 2025, <https://www.mybib.com/#/projects/om3edb/citations/new/report>; Michelle Black, Lana Obradovic, and Deanna House, “Behind the Curve: Technology Challenges Facing the Homeland Intelligence and Counterterrorism Workforce,” *Journal of Cybersecurity* 10, no. 1 (January 1, 2024), <https://doi.org/10.1093/cybsec/tyae002>.

Misperceptions of the relationship between CI and other security functions further complicate implementing counterintelligence practices. Without a clear theoretical framework or centralized approach, CI remains poorly understood and inconsistently applied. Clarifying the role of CI as a separate function from general security measures and aligning it with the operational needs of academia and industry will be essential for building stronger defenses against foreign exploitation.

If effective CI measures in both the private and public sectors are not established, U.S. innovation, technology, and intellectual property will remain exposed. Institutions must find a balance between openness and security. Addressing misperceptions of counterintelligence and strengthening cooperation between government agencies and civilian sectors will be critical to closing the gap, protecting U.S. strategic interests, and strengthening national resilience.

Description of Research Study

This study is composed of two anonymous surveys to evaluate CI literacy, perceived relevance, and factors influencing its implementation within civilian organizations. The surveys were sent to a total of 171 individuals eighteen years of age or older in the academic and corporate sectors. Fifty of those participants were randomly selected to complete the qualitative survey. The participants were recruited by the undergraduate interns involved in the study.

The quantitative survey involved a series of demographic questions, multiple-choice questions, rating scales, and selected open ended questions to collect the respondents' personal understanding of counterintelligence, institutional attitudes of counterintelligence, and awareness of foreign threats to U.S. innovation and intellectual property. Participants were asked to score statements relating to counterintelligence and foreign threats on a scale of one (strongly disagree)

to five (strongly agree) with the final question allowing the participants to add any final thoughts or concerns that were not covered in the survey questions.

The qualitative survey involved a randomly selected, smaller number of respondents who were asked about their views of counterintelligence in their respective sectors and suggestions for expanding understanding of counterintelligence practices. In addition to demographic questions, the survey questions posed to the respondents required freeform answers that allowed the participants to elaborate in more depth on their views of counterintelligence, its role in their sectors, and their view of measures that can be taken to implement or educate individuals in their sector about counterintelligence practices.

Quantitative Results

Research Methodology

For the quantitative portion of this research, surveys were distributed to 121 individuals who were professionals in both academic and corporate organizations as well as nonprofits, public service, and other areas of the private sector. All responses were anonymous to protect participants' identities. The survey questions were grouped into five categories to identify general demographic details and assess participants' CI knowledge, views on the relevance of CI to their sector, perceptions of the current threat landscape, and perceived organizational attitudes towards counterintelligence.

The survey began with the participants confirming their age to be over eighteen and their consent to participate, followed by a series of demographic questions asking each participant to indicate his or her age, highest education level, employment sector, current role in his or her organization, and years of work experience in his or her sector.

The subsequent section assessed the respondents' views and knowledge of CI. Participants were asked to define counterintelligence in their own words, followed by a series of multiple-choice questions about their primary exposure to and knowledge of counterintelligence. Additional questions asked participants to rate responses on a scale of one (strong disagreement) to five (strong agreement) to assess their confidence in knowledge of counterintelligence and relevance to their sector.

Participants then answered rating scale and multiple-choice questions about their perception of the threat posed by foreign intelligence activities, their level of concern about insider threats, and their awareness of foreign adversaries conducting intelligence operations in the United States. Additional questions included participants' views on the inclusion of CI training in the workplace and willingness to participate in such training programs if offered.

Further multiple-choice and rating scale questions explored broader organizational views: participants were asked their views on whether their organization invests resources in counterintelligence, how colleagues and leadership view counterintelligence, and the costs and benefits of adopting counterintelligence programs in their organizations.

The final section asked participants their assessment on whether counterintelligence is a critical issue for the United States and whether their institutions were properly protected from foreign intelligence threats. The final question allowed participants to add any final thoughts or concerns that were not addressed in the survey.

After collecting all participants' responses, the data was comparatively analyzed across sectors. Key points of analysis included perceived organizational protection against foreign intelligence threats, the relationship between years of experience and perceived threat levels, and

sector-specific trends. This data was converted into graphs to provide a visual representation showcasing key findings.

Corporate Sector

A total of 44 participants from the corporate sector responded to the survey, representing 60.3% of the 73 responses. The age range of respondents spanned from under 25 to over 65, with a majority over 45 years of age. Twenty-four respondents had more than 20 years in their field, indicating an experienced cohort. Roles included entry-level employees, experienced staff, security/compliance personnel, mid-level managers, and executives. Notably, 19 of the 44 respondents held executive or senior leadership roles, while only one respondent identified as working in security/compliance.

When asked whether their institution was adequately protected from foreign intelligence threats, most corporate respondents were uncertain: 23 selected “maybe,” compared to 12 who said “yes” and 9 who said “no.” Interestingly, this sector still rated itself as the most adequately protected relative to other sectors (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1: Belief that institutions are adequately protected from foreign intelligence risks?

The belief in adequate protection from foreign intelligence risks within the private sector may come from the perception of resource investment into CI or insider threat programs. The private sector invests more resources into these programs, as 18 respondents answered “yes”, compared to academia, where 3 said “yes”. An additional 13 respondents said “maybe,” showing increased likelihood of investment in CI awareness. Meanwhile, 13 people responded “no”. This is a rise in the “no” category for this graph, as compared to the “no” section of *Figure 2*.

Figure 2: *Institutions currently investing resources into CI or insider threat programs*

Respondents indicate that the perceived benefit of CI is stronger in the corporate sector. On a scale of 1 to 5, 32 respondents rated the benefits of CI as 3 or higher, with 20 giving a rating of 4 or 5. Only 12 respondents rated the benefits of CI below 3, and two people gave the lowest rating of 1. In contrast, in the academic sector, only four respondents rated CI benefits as 4 or higher (*Figure 3*). This may indicate a greater interest in or perceived benefit of CI in the private sector compared to academia.

Figure 3: Belief in the cost/benefit of CI

When asked whether foreign adversaries were targeting trade secrets or intellectual property in their sector, most corporate respondents agreed. Fourteen selected “agree” and six “strongly agree,” compared to eight who disagreed and three who strongly disagreed and thirteen participants who chose to remain neutral. Overall, 33 of 44 either agreed or were neutral, indicating a heightened awareness of CI risks by foreign intelligence services in the corporate sector.

When asked what would make CI most worth the investment, respondents selected “clear examples of financial or reputational damage from CI failures.” When told they could select up to three options each, 32 people selected this option. This option was clearly the most important to respondents. As the next closest option, “case studies of successful CI programs in similar organizations,” was selected by 18 people. The culmination of the data gathered suggests that people in the private sector think CI is an issue where the benefits outweigh the costs, and those costs are a worthwhile investment.

Academic Sector

Twenty individuals from the academic sector participated in the survey, representing 27.4% of the 73 respondents. Most respondents in this cohort, 75%, held faculty or research

roles, and all had worked in their fields for at least six years. Other roles included mid-level managers, experienced staff, executives, and entry-level positions, which were primarily held by individuals with at least six years of experience.

When asked to define counterintelligence in their own words, most academic respondents described it as either the protection of the United States or the gathering of intelligence. When given multiple-choice definitions, all but one correctly identified CI as “preventing foreign interference and insider threats.” Nineteen of the 20 had heard of CI before, most commonly through the media. Four had encountered it through formal education or training. Despite this familiarity, 16 respondents rated their understanding of CI between 1 and 3 on a 5-point scale.

Academics largely viewed CI as irrelevant to their day-to-day work. Additionally, many individuals were not concerned with insider threats, but they did believe that foreign adversaries could be targeting secrets in their sector. Sixteen rated its relevance between 1 and 3; only four rated it as 3. Similarly, fifteen were unconcerned about insider threats, rating their concern as a 1 or 2. However, twelve participants agreed or strongly agreed that foreign adversaries could be targeting academic research.

While many indicated awareness of foreign intelligence threats in their sector, half of the participants stated that their work does not invest resources in counterintelligence. Only three individuals reported that their institution invests in CI, while seven said “maybe.” Twelve said they were “maybe” adequately protected, while five felt they were not (*Figure 4*).

Figure 4: *Academic professionals' response to whether their institutions invest resources into counterintelligence.*

When asked what would convince their institution to invest in CI, the most common answer chosen was “clear examples of financial or reputational damage from CI failures,” followed by “clear examples of financial or reputational damage from CI failures, case studies of successful CI programs in similar organizations, and sector-specific threat briefings.” The responses indicate that real scenarios and case studies highlighting the threats posed to their sector would be a valuable tool in increasing awareness and understanding of counterintelligence.

Other Sectors: Nonprofit, Public Service, Healthcare, and More

Participants from additional sectors included three respondents from nonprofits, two retired professionals, and the remaining consisted of employees from government contracting, health insurance, healthcare research, and retail. When asked how relevant CI is to their work, seven of these nine individuals rated its importance between 1 and 3. When asked if their

organization invests resources into counterintelligence, five of the nine participants stated that their organization does while three said that their organization does not.

Qualitative Results

Research Methodology

In the qualitative portion of this research, the survey was distributed to fifty participants across various academic and corporate sectors with identities remaining anonymous for personal protection. The survey began by asking participants to confirm they were over the age of eighteen, confirmed their participation in the survey, and was then distributed into six sections. It is important to note that participants did not have a minimum or maximum word count for their responses to any questions.

The first section concerned demographics and asked participants to answer questions identifying their current professional role or title, the type of institution or sector they work in, the amount of time they have worked in their field, and their highest level of education.

Following demographics, the questions concerned knowledge of counterintelligence and prompted participants to, in their own words, describe what counterintelligence means to them, where, if anywhere, they first encountered the concept of counterintelligence, the types of threats they associate with counterintelligence concerns, and if they believed CI is relevant to their field or institution and why or why not.

The next series of questions asked participants to explain, in their own words, if they think foreign adversaries are targeting their sector and why or why not, how they would compare U.S. values or security practices to those of U.S. adversaries (e.g. China, Russia) when it comes to protecting information or intellectual property, and whether they believe CI awareness should be more widely integrated into professional settings like their own and why or why not.

Further questions examined organizational culture and CI implementation. Participants were asked to respond whether their institution or employer ever offered training or policy materials related to insider threats or CI. Following this, participants were asked to explain, in their own words, what they would say is the general attitude toward CI or security measures in their workplace, if CI is not emphasized where they work, why they believed that is, and what barriers might prevent an organization like theirs from implementing CI measures.

In the final section, participants were asked what they would recommend to government or private leaders to improve CI awareness across society, if there are specific tools, messages, or platforms they think would help reach their sector more effectively, and if there is anything else they would like to share about CI, foreign threats, or organizational preparedness.

Demographics

Seventeen participants responded to the survey, representing 34% of the total sample. The respondents to the qualitative survey varied in their industry, role, and education. This variance generally followed the ideal parameters for a participant of the study, with very few outliers. Generally, participants were selected from individuals in private industry and academia who hold white-collar or experienced positions in their fields.

The academic sector had a total of seven participants. Six of the seven participants held a Ph.D. while the single outlier held a master's degree. The private industry had a total of ten participants: one with some college but no degree, one with work-related certificates but no degree, one with an associate's degree, four with a bachelor's degree, two with a master's degree, and one with a Ph.D. This follows what would be expected from a mix of workers from academia and private industry (*Figure 5*).

Figure 5: Education Demographics by Highest Level of Education

Regarding leadership, a far larger portion of those in private industry held leadership positions compared to those employed by a university. None of the participants employed in public service holds a leadership position (*Figure 6*).

Figure 6: Employment Demographics

Participant Knowledge of Counterintelligence

The respondents described various ways in which they first perceived counterintelligence. Most reported that their initial exposure was through media sources such as spy movies, war television shows, and books. Nine total respondents discovered CI through

media, three from academia, and three from the private sector learned about CI from their workplace. One academic mentioned they had first learned about CI from their high school education, citing the Cold War as a significant area studied. A few other respondents reported independent study through personal interests that contributed to their development of CI knowledge.

In terms of how these perceptions shaped their perspectives, respondents demonstrated a diverse understanding of CI threats. These CI threats were recognized as digital and physical. Their concerns of CI ranged from different levels; they varied from state-level espionage and cybercrime to personal and work-related issues like scams, disinformation, sabotage, and data security. Their different experiences demonstrate the respondents' understanding of CI, as well as how their personal experiences with the workplace, media, and personal interests shape their perception of CI threats.

Previous Counterintelligence Training

Participants were asked to respond yes, no, or maybe if their workplace had ever offered training or policy materials related to insider threats or CI. Half of the private sector respondents have received prior training while the other half have not. In academia, two reported to have had prior training; four reported having no training, and one has possibly had training (*Figure 7*).

Figure 7: Previous CI Training

Threat Environment

When asked what types of threats participants associated with CI, similar responses were given. All but three respondents associated CI threats with data breaches, such as hacking and stealing proprietary information. Three other participants provided answers that included aspects of physical violence, such as assassinations and terrorism.

In the case of active threats, all but one participant in the private sector answered that foreign adversaries are targeting their sector. In academia, four professionals do believe foreign adversaries are targeting their sector, with one noting research institutes are more susceptible to targeting, and two participants do not believe their sector is a target of foreign adversaries. One academic participant provided a politically driven response and did not state if his or her sector was a target.

When asked to compare U.S. values or security practices to those of U.S. adversaries, most respondents, particularly those from the private industry, believe the U.S. loses too much intellectual property to foreign adversaries. Two respondents mentioned that the U.S. has become accustomed to selling private data without knowing where or why the information is being used and believe this is a security threat. Two respondents mentioned the intellectual losses the U.S. has lost to China in the tech world, while one response mentioned Russia as a “flip flop” adversary of the U.S. 3 participants believe

that U.S. security practices have slipped in recent years, and leadership have not addressed this issue enough while another three believe the U.S. had strict regulations. Four participants were not sure or could not respond to the prompt.

When asked if participants believed CI awareness should be more widely integrated into professional settings like theirs, most agreed that awareness should be widely integrated. From the private sector, all but 2 participants believe that CI awareness is needed in the workplace. One outlier did not think CI should be implemented but did believe IT databases should be better protected. The other respondent admitted they were not well-versed enough to provide a suggestion. In academia, three participants recommended CI awareness be more widely integrated, while two did not believe it should be for fear of a “spy state” atmosphere that may be created in the workplace. Two respondents from academia were unsure if CI awareness should be implemented.

Institutional Barriers to Implementing Counterintelligence Measures

When asked what barriers might prevent participants’ organizations from implementing CI measures, only two respondents claimed they did not see any, one in academia and one in private industry, and one private industry respondent said they did not know. It is also worth noting that one respondent, an academia professional, said the barrier was that CI was unnecessary. Four respondents mentioned a lack of understanding of the true nature of foreign intelligence threats and the necessity of CI measures for their specific industry. Of those four, one was in academia, and three were in private industry.

Four respondents, three in the private sector and one in academia, mentioned financial barriers to CI with one private sector respondent noting that although it may be costly, it would not be as costly as a major security breach. A couple of respondents mentioned a lack of training or lack of knowledge to train employees as well as ethics being a barrier. No answer had a majority response, so to summarize, the major barriers to implementing CI measures are a lack

of understanding the nature of foreign threats to participants' organizations, lack of understanding the necessity of CI and training materials, financial barriers, and ethical considerations of trust.

Participant Recommendations

The recommendations varied among respondents, with fifteen participants offering in-depth ideas and two offering no advice. Prior exposure, personal definitions of counterintelligence, and professional sector impacted responses, with those in academia encouraging transparency from the government in multiple recommendations and those in industry focused on case studies and how counterintelligence can be used as an intangible asset in their organization.

When asked about what would change someone's mind within their organization to implement counterintelligence practices, common responses were to build trust within the organization, to provide evidence that their organization was at risk of foreign interference, case examples of organizations that did not implement counterintelligence practices and were victims of foreign interference, and education or training on counterintelligence offered from professional organizations.

Respondents who did not find counterintelligence relevant to their sector, which came solely from academia, suggested breaches, threats, and trust building as actions that would likely change the minds of those in their organization. Those in academia with at least 15 years of experience in their position and who hold a PhD. emphasized education and assessment of potential breaches. Those from the corporate sector, of whom none had more than 25 years of experience, stated that the financial impacts of not implementing counterintelligence and case studies would be most influential in changing the minds of others within their organization.

Potential evidence that could be presented to the respondent's organization's leadership to make counterintelligence more compelling was then asked for from respondents. Nearly all respondents suggested that examples of what could happen to their organization if counterintelligence was not implemented would be most effective. Other responses included how counterintelligence could provide a competitive advantage in their industry, quarterly reports on potential risks to their industry, and to trust that the federal government is not using counterintelligence to spy on them. Those who discussed how counterintelligence would provide a competitive advantage came from an industry background, indicating that leadership is merely focused on what will provide higher profits, not necessarily how to protect them. Those who had a good understanding of what counterintelligence is exclusively believed that case studies or examples of detrimental effects of not implementing counterintelligence would be most effective to present to leadership.

When asked for recommendations for government or private leaders to improve counterintelligence awareness throughout society, many respondents agreed that encouraging communication in and outside of the workplace would be beneficial. Many emphasized transparency and building trust between the government and private/academia sectors would allow for easier discussion about counterintelligence. One respondent from academia encouraged the study of multiple languages to decrease the need for spying and understanding of cross-cultural experiences. A Chief Financial Officer with more than 15 years of experience commented that the idea that the United States is in an "intellectual Cold War with China" should be emphasized by government leaders. One professional in the corporate sector with 10 years of experience suggested modernized legislation to promote privacy, as privacy is a "top down" idea that needs to be exemplified by government leadership.

Respondents were then asked if there were any specific tools, messages, or platforms that they believed would help reach their respective sectors more efficiently. Most were unsure of any specific examples to give, but those that did have suggestions had varied answers. Some ideas included social media, traditional news sources, company newsletters, and memoranda sent from professional organizations such as think tanks. Those that recommended company newsletters work in the corporate sector while all other recommendations came from both the corporate sector and academia.

Key Findings

The results of the quantitative and qualitative surveys provide important insight into challenges faced when promoting counterintelligence measures in the academic and corporate sectors. The key findings based on the responses are summarized below:

The surveys indicate that initial exposure to counterintelligence is strongly linked to popular media. While many respondents in the corporate sector appear to be exposed to counterintelligence practices through company training modules, movies and TV shows portraying dramatized scenes of espionage still play a significant role in developing the public's general perception of counterintelligence.

Respondents involved in the corporate sector were more likely than respondents in academia to view counterintelligence as important for their work and national security. Many respondents believe that counterintelligence is relevant to their work field, recognizing the importance of protecting sensitive information, maintaining company-wide and nationwide security, as well as securing operations. This has been consistent in all the sectors in which the respondents took part.

However, respondents in academia were less likely to view counterintelligence as vital to their field. These individuals viewed CI as a tool that was not in line with their daily responsibilities in the academic workplace, perceiving it as a tool being more useful in intelligence and national security rather than academic study or teaching. The variation of these two beliefs indicates how the workplace of an individual influences their perception of how relevant CI is in their daily lives. Several respondents cited an inability or lack of care on the part of leadership or their superiors to pursue such an initiative. Whether or not the private and university spheres are ready to implement counterintelligence practices or hire a firm to implement said practices is mixed.

The academic sector faces significant challenges in bringing awareness to counterintelligence. Some academic professionals believed counterintelligence implementation would be a way for the government to spy on the work of universities and others suggested transparency from the government when communicating threats and downplaying conspiracy theories. One respondent stated that attempts to implement counterintelligence in academia by the government would be selfish of them and would be done merely for self-profit.

Those in the corporate sector also discussed better communication from government leadership regarding counterintelligence but not as strongly or as often as those from the academic sector. The corporate sector was not as concerned with transparency but focused on the need for an increase in education on the threats to their sector that counterintelligence could prevent.

The financial ability to support counterintelligence programs remains a large hurdle for both academic and corporate institutions with limited budgets. Some respondents in academia indicated a lack of funding for counterintelligence measures. Smaller academic

institutions in particular do not have the financial budget needed for formal counterintelligence programs, leaving them vulnerable to foreign threats.

Strategic Recommendations

Improving the perception and implementation of CI in academic and corporate sectors requires a multipronged approach that focuses on reframing, integration, and education. The United States' adversaries use a whole-of-government approach to target the homeland's vulnerabilities and hubs of information, requiring a whole-of-society approach to combat these threats and mitigate academic and corporate vulnerabilities.⁷ Adopting this approach would emphasize and facilitate coordinated engagement and cooperation between the various levels of government, academia, and the corporate sector.

To overcome distrust and resistance, CI must first be reframed in a way that resonates with each sector's core mission and language. In academia, CI should be represented as a safeguard for intellectual property and academic integrity rather than a tool for government surveillance. It is necessary to show how government involvement would aim to introduce a plan of action to protect research and innovative ideas while not restricting academic freedom. Due to the often-skeptical nature of academia's perception of government interference, CI could be distanced from governmental actions, instead being framed as security measures taken independently. In contrast, the corporate sector would benefit from positioning CI as a strategic asset that protects profit margins and helps maintain a competitive edge. Identifying vulnerable assets valuable to a company, integrating security elements, and engaging with external intelligence, federal, law enforcement, and industry security forces would be a suitable CI plan to

⁷ "National Counterintelligence Strategy 2024," ODNI, August 2024, https://www.dni.gov/files/NCSC/documents/features/NCSC_CI_Strategy-pages-20240730.pdf: 19-20.

be proposed.⁸ To motivate leaders to support CI initiatives, reframing efforts should highlight its ability to mitigate financial and reputational risks that come with data leaks and stolen intellectual property. This reframing makes CI relevant and valuable to each sector's priorities.

Second, a more thorough integration of CI into organizational structures is critical for practical implementation. CI must be integrated into the already existing nature and thought processes of these two sectors to counter foreign espionage effectively. Academic institutions could embed CI awareness within existing structures of security and academic integrity, which could be as simple as instituting multi-factor authentication processes. Meanwhile, CI could be incorporated into established cybersecurity, risk management, and insider threat programs in the corporate sector. Integrating CI into routine security audits, for example, would ensure that it becomes a natural part of organizational operations without excessive disruption. By normalizing CI strategies within day-to-day operations, these measures become independent from the government and allow organizations to build their own resilience to foreign espionage.

Third, a concerted effort to educate clients who may not understand how their enterprises fit within a national security perspective. In some cases, it may be necessary to address specific cases of successful security breaches that resulted in losses of intellectual property when engaging with clients. It would be important to highlight the quantifiable losses in revenue and reputation because of previous CI failures to establish relevance to clients, especially those in corporate environments. Additionally, including examples of successful implementations of CI measures that prevented theft of intellectual property in corporate and academic settings would be educational and persuasive. Cooperation between the National Counterintelligence and

⁸ John Slattery, "Economic Espionage and the Growing Case for Corporate Counterintelligence," The Security Executive Council, accessed July 8, 2025.

Security Center, National Counterintelligence Task Force, private sector, and academia to expand partnerships, improving information safeguarding capabilities and awareness, would similarly reduce reluctance to adopt CI programs. Awareness of proper CI measures and the existing threats to academia and corporations directly contributes to the successful implementation of measures imperative for enhancing national security.

Limitations

Due to timeline and data collection constraints, analysis is somewhat limited. The survey had 73 quantitative responses, which is a sufficient sample size for calculating averages and observing general trends. However, the statistical power of this sample drops when divided into small subgroups such as type of job, level of education, and age. For the qualitative aspect of the survey, there were 17 total respondents, a sufficient sample size for thematic analysis. These results allowed the researchers to highlight patterns, themes, and insights from the target population, but the overall generalizability of these findings is limited. If this topic were to be studied further, a larger sample size would enable researchers to explore different industries in the private sector and various academic institutions in greater detail and ensure that relevant perspectives are not overlooked.

Additionally, the participants for this survey were recruited through research interns' personal connections. This shared connection to the interns limits the external validity of this research, as results reflect perceptions within this specific network. Although the interns come from a variety of hometowns and undergraduate universities, further research should use a more random sampling method to enhance external validity.

Finally, because the surveys were anonymized, there was no opportunity to conduct post-survey interviews and debrief participants. The inability to conduct post-survey interviews with

participants in the qualitative data group limited the opportunity to explore unexpected themes in greater depth. Future research should include surveys with specific modifications that do not require anonymity, facilitating the conduct of interviews, and yielding a greater depth and level of nuance in the results.

Conclusion

Every day, the United States faces malign threats by foreign intelligence services in every sector of society. Private corporation and academia are the heart of American innovation and research that has led to U.S. dominance on the world stage. Foreign adversaries are also advancing their own operations against both public and private sectors to steal American intellectual property and sabotage our most critical areas.

Counterintelligence practices and programs are the solution to identifying threats to our critical infrastructure and innovations as well as protect and deter those threats from succeeding. This study demonstrates that the non-government sectors have some awareness of the threats at hand, but there is still more work to do to incentivize and demonstrate the effectiveness of CI measures. This study provides an initial step in identifying perceptions of counterintelligence among academia and private companies and what we can do to bring awareness to the importance of using CI.

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